

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1965	Paulin G. Djité	1985	1985			Ivory Coast-Australian sociolinguist, translator	
1965	Louise McNally	1986	1992		w	American linguist (Semantics and Pragmatics)	
1965	John McWhorter	1986	1993			American linguist, associate professor of English and comparative literature	
1965	Jussi Karlgren	1988	2000			Swedish computational linguist, adjunct professor at KTH, and co-founder of text analytics company Gavagai AB	
1965	Ignatius Swart	1988				South African Professor, Department of Religion & Theology	
1965	Jeroen van de Weijer	1989	1995			Dutch linguist	
1965	Kira Hall	1989	1995		w	American professor of Linguistics and Anthropology, as well as director for the Program in Culture, Language, and Social Practice (CLASP)	
1965	Alexandra Brewis Slade	1989	1992		w	New Zealand anthropologist who studies how health reflects the interaction of human biology and culture	
1965	Jean-Luc Fournet	1989	1995			French papyrologist	
1965	Meylaerts Reine	1990	1998		w	Belgian full professor Comparative Literature, translator	
1965	Reine Meylaerts	1990	1998		w	Belgian Professor of Comparative Literature and Translation Studies	
1965	Bogdanka Pavelin Lešić	1990	1994		w	Croatian Full professor at the Chair for French Language	
1965	Eva Horn	1990	1996		w	German cultural and literary scholar and university professor	
1965	Игорь Лоцилов	1990	1997			Russian literature critic (Сибирь, поэзия)	
1965	Antonio Fuccillo	1990	1996			Italian full professor of law and religion	
1965	Christopher D Manning	1991	1994			American Computer Science and Linguistics	
1965	Simon Philip Botley	1991	2000			British linguist	
1965	Robert Vilain	1991	1991			British professor (German, Austrian, French and Comparative Literature in the 19th and early 20th centuries, and in lyric poetry)	
1965	Ivana Kolářová	1991	1993		w	Czech researcher of Department of Czech Language and Literature	

1965	Alessandro Capone	1991	1998		Italian linguist	
1965	Toshiaki Kimura	1991	2014		Japanese Professor, Graduate School of Arts and Letters (religion)	
1965	Peter Ackema	1991	1995		Dutch Professor of Linguistics and English Language	
1965	Alexandre Negreiros	1991	No		Brazilian keyboardist, composer, arranger and music producer	
1965	Armando Salvatore	1991			Italian Professor of Global Religious Studies	
1965	Paula Fikkert	1992	1994	w	Dutch Professor First Language Acquisition and Phonology	
1965	Ioannis Telelis	1992	1995		Greek researcher in Byzantine Philology, Philosophy and History	
1965	Aðalheiður Guðmundsdóttir	1992	1993	w	Icelandic professor of medieval Icelandic literature	
1965	Arok Wolvengrey	1992	2011		Canadian linguist (Cree language, syntax, Native American languages, lexicography)	
1965	Balthasar Bickel	1992	1997		Swiss linguist (language typology, Kiranti languages)	
1965	Metin Boşnak	1992	1996		Bosnian-Turkish scholar of american studies and comparative literature, and published poet	
1965	Ольга Владимировна Тиханова	1992	1992		Russian assistant professor of Department of History and Typology of Russian and Foreign Literature	
1965	Steven Weitzman	1992			American Professor of Religious Studies	
1965	Adrian Randolph	1993	1995		American Professor of Art History	
1965	Gayane R. Hovhannisyan	1993	1993	w	Armenian Professor of General and Applied Linguistics	
1965	Diane Watt	1993	1993	w	British medievalist, currently Professor of Medieval English Literature	
1965	Hashim Ismail	1993	2003		Indonesian Professor of Department of Literature, Academy of Malay Studies	
1965	Ken Lunde	1993	1994		American specialist in information processing for East Asian languages	
1965	Jonathan M. Hess	1993	1993	2018	American philologist	1965-2018
1965	John McWhorter	1993	1993		American academic and linguist, associate professor of English and comparative literature	
1965	Lynne Murphy	1993	1995	w	American professor of linguistics	
1965	Nora Lafi	1993	1999	w	French reseracher of Centre for Modern Oriental Studies	

1965	Asbjørn Dyrendal	1993			Norwegian professor of Department of Philosophy and Religious Studies	
1965	Richard Rogers	1994	1994		American Professor of New Media & Digital Culture	
1965	Jane Stuart-Smith	1994	1995	w	British Professor of Phonetics and Sociolinguistics (English Language & Linguistics)	
1965	Guadalupe Arbona Abascal	1994	1994	w	Spanish Professor of Literature	
1965	Anna Lisa Tota	1994	1994	w	Swiss Professor of Cultural sociology	
1965	Sevim Aslan	1994	1996	w	Turkish Associate professor of Fine Arts (carpets)	
1965	Marius Kwint	1994	1994		British Cultural historian and Senior Lecturer in Visual Culture	
1965	Sudipa Ray Bandyopadhyay	1994	1996	w	Indian Professor in Ancient Indian History and Culture	
1965	Oliver Grau	1994	1999		German art historian and media theoretician with a focus on image science, modernity and media art as well as culture	
1965	Joshua Landy	1995	1997		American the Andrew B. Hammond Professor in French Language, Literature and Civilization	
1965	Nicole Hewitt	1995	2013	w	British-Croatian visual artist (film, video, installation, performance and text)	
1965	Miklós Vörös	1995	2001		Hungarian sociologist and cultural anthropologist, cultural heritage and cultural policy expert	
1965	Igor Loshchilov	1995	1997		Russian literature critic (история русской литературы, авангард, поэзия, Сибирь)	
1965	Helma Van den Berg	1995	1995	2003 w	Dutch linguist specializing in Caucasian languages	1965-2003
1965	David Dinwoodie	1995	1995		American anthropologist specializing in the Chilcotin First Nation in British Columbia, Canada	
1965	Ida Marie Høeg	1995	2008	w	Norwegian Professor of Sociology of Religion	
1965	Matthew C. Strecher	1996	1996		American Professor of Modern Japanese Literature	
1965	Andra Kalnača	1996	1997	w	Latvian linguist and educator	
1965	Lalith Ananda	1996	2013		Sri Lankan Senior Lecturer in Linguistics	
1965	Elizabeth Solopova	1996	2009	w	British philologist and medievalist	
1965	Sarah Clackson	1996	1996	w	British foremost Coptologist	1965-2003
1965	Annette Merz	1996	2001	w	German Protestant theologian and biblical scholar	
1965	Cynthia Becker	1997	2000	w	American Associate Professor of Art History	

1965	Adriana Lucaciu	1997	2005	w	Romanian Professor of Faculty of Arts and Design
1965	Sharyn Clough	1997	1997	w	American professor at School of History, Philosophy, and Religion
1965	Matthias Henze	1997	1997		German the Isla Carroll and Perry E. Turner Professor of Hebrew Bible and Early Judaism
1965	Karl Katschthaler	1998	1998		Hungarian Associate Professor of Literature
1965	Dusadee Swangviboonpong	1998	2000		Thai Reseacher associate (Music and culture of Thailand, Laos and Cambodia)
1965	Pere Comellas	1999	2005		Spanish researcher in Sociolinguistics, Anthropological Linguistics and Translation Studies
1965	Irina Antanasijević	1999	1999	w	Serbian-Russian born linguist
1965	Richard von Georgi	1999	1999		German Head of MA study program Media Psychology with the main focus on Psychology of Music
1965	John W Krummel	1999			American Associate Professor, Religious Studies
1965	Alexandra Grieser	1999	2005	w	German Assistant Professor Theory of Religion
1965	José Antonio Alonso Navarro	2000	2012		Spanish philologist, medievalist, a translator, and a writer
1965	Caroline Wilkinson	2000	2000		British anthropologist (forensic facial reconstruction)
1965	Abdul Aziz Ali al-Harbi	2001	2001		Saudi Arabian Islamic scholar
1965	Adenike Akinjobi	2002	2004	w	Nigerian Professor of English Phonology
1965	Suleiman Norein Osman Eldai	2002	2002		Sudanese Associate Professor of English Language
1965	Kedrick James	2003	2009		Canadian researcher (digitally enhanced data analysis, visualization, sonification and performance) exploration of media poetics, language and literacy education, network theory, arts-based communities and marginalized voices in mass media)
1965	Mohammad Al-Badawi	2006	2011		Sudanese linguist and publisher, singer and composer
1965	Maniraj Sukdaven	2006	2014		South African Senior Lecturer in Religion Studies
1965	Asma Mundrawala	2007	2010	w	Indian visual artist and theater practitioner
1965	Yayo Herrero	2007	No	w	Spanish anthropologist, engineer, professor and ecofeminist activist
1965	Deborah Hyde	2009		w	British sceptic, folklorist, cultural anthropologist, fellow of the Committee for Skeptical Inquiry, and editor-in-chief of The Skeptic

1965	Ralph Klewitz	2013	2018		Swiss Artist, designer, academic, researcher	
1966	Shahab Ahmed	1987	1999	2015	Pakistani-American scholar of Islam	1966-2015
1966	Shadi Bartsch	1989	1992	w	American academic and is the Helen A. Regenstein Distinguished Service Professor of Classics	
1966	Simon Dixon	1990	1994		British director of Centre for Digital Music (Music Informatics, music information retrieval, sound and music computing, audio signal processing)	
1966	Ermanno Malaspina	1990	1999		Italian Academicus ordinarius at the Pontificia Academia Latinitatis (Vatican City) and Latin Language and Literature Associate Professor	
1966	Anthea Van Jaarsveld	1990	1995	w	South African Senior Lecturer at University of the Free State	
1966	Miriam Butt	1991	1993	w	German Professor of Computational and Theoretical Linguistics	
1966	Elena Berezovich	1991	1992	w	Russian linguist known for her work in onomastics, etymology, and ethnolinguistics	
1966	Heather Burke	1991	1997	w	Australian historical archaeologist and an Associate Professor in the College of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences	
1966	Caterina Magni	1991	1994	w	Italian-French archaeologist and anthropologist, who specialises in the study of pre-Columbian cultures of Mesoamerica, and in particular the iconography, art and mythology and religion of the Olmec civilization	
1966	Lee D. Baker	1991	1994		American cultural anthropologist	
1966	Bülent Şenay	1991	1999		Turkish professor of history of religion	
1966	Sarah Pink	1992	1996	w	Australian social anthropologist	
1966	Marianne Hundt	1992	1996	w	German Professor of English Linguistics	
1966	Elena Lvovna Berezovich	1992	1992	w	Russian linguist (onomastics, etymology, and ethnolinguistics)	
1966	Mary Bucholtz	1992	1997	w	American linguist	
1966	Joseph Dumit	1992			American cultural anthropologist and science and technology studies scholar	
1966	Michael Atwood Mason	1992	1997		American folklorist and museum professional	

1966	Stephen Asma	1993	1993		American Professor of Philosophy (life sciences, and Religion and Science, especially Buddhism and Christianity)
1966	Marco... Giannotti	1993	2006		Brazilian Professor of art (Postwar & Contemporary artist)
1966	Anastasia Giannakidou	1993	1997	w	Greek professor of linguistics
1966	Tuc Ho-Dac	1993	1996		Vietnamese linguist
1966	Scott Jarvis	1993	1997		American linguist
1966	Norma Mendoza-Denton	1993	1997	w	American professor of anthropokogy (sociophonetics, language and identity, ethnography and visual anthropology)
1966	Jill Morford	1993	1993	w	American professor of linguistics (understanding of language acquisition by studying communication in the visual modality)
1966	Kamari Maxine Clarke	1993	1998	w	Canadian-American specialist on theories of legal pluralism, international justice, and social theory
1966	Brian Stiltner	1993	1997		American Professor of Theology and Religious Studies
1966	Mikita Brottman	1994	1994	w	British American non-fiction author, scholar, and psychologist known for her interest in true crime
1966	Péter Szigetvári	1994	2000		Hungarian linguist
1966	Ricard Mas	1994	1999		Spanish art historian
1966	Alla Zagaykevych	1994	1994	w	Ukrainian composer of contemporary classical music, performance artist, organiser of electroacoustic music projects, musicologist
1966	Catherine Mary Conybeare	1994	1997	w	British academic and philologist
1966	Lucien Castaing-Taylor	1994	2000		British anthropologist and artist who works in film, video, and photography
1966	Nathalie Luca	1994	1994	w	French research director at the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), an anthropologist and a sociologist of religions
1966	Jane Setter	1995	2001	w	British phonetician
1966	Юсупова Альфия Шавкетовна	1995	1995	w	Russian philologist and educator

1966	Iulia Narcisa Cibisescu Duran	1995	No	w	Romanian Composer, Conductor, Lecturer dr., Pianist, Poet
1966	Mart Velsker	1995	2005		Estonian lecturer in Estonian Literature
1966	Francesco Ardolino	1996	2002		Italian Professor Aggregate of Italian Philology
1966	Christina Maranci	1996	1998	w	Armenian-American researcher, writer, translator, historian, and professor
1966	David Odo	1997	2004		American Director of Academic and Public Programs, Division Head and Research Curator, Harvard Art Museums
1966	K. David Harrison	1997	2000		Canadian linguist, anthropologist, author and activist for the documentation and preservation of endangered languages
1966	Thomas J. Pluckhahn	1997	2002		American assistant professor of the Department of Anthropology
1966	Benoît Pellistrandi	1997	1997		French historian and hispanist
1966	Enrique Santos Unamuno	1998	1998		Spanish Professor of Comparative Literature
1966	Nicola Denzey Lewis	1998	1998	w	American the Margo L. Goldsmith Chair in Women's Studies in Religion
1966	Tess Lea	1999	2002	w	Australian anthropologist (anthropology of policy)
1966	Gina Athena Ulysse	1999	1999	w	Haitian-American anthropologist, feminist, poet, performance artist and activist.
1966	Vedad Spahić	1999			Bosnian Full Professor, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
1966	Clifford E Nwanna	2000	2002		Nigerian Professor, Department of Fine and Applied Arts (sculpture)
1966	Iman Adawy Ahmed Hanafy	2000	2000	w	Egyptian Professor of English Literature
1966	Reda.A. H. Mahmoud	2000	2002		Egyptian Professor of Linguistics
1966	T. J. Demos	2000	2000		British art historian and cultural critic who writes on contemporary art and visual culture, particularly in relation to globalization, politics, migration and ecology
1966	Sorin Crişan	2001	2001		Romanian professor of art history, Rector of the Tîrgu-Mureş University of Arts (history, aesthetics and philosophy of theater, psychodrama and psychoanalysis)

1966	Ziad Fahed	2001	2001		Lebanese Associate Professor of Religious studies
1966	Golnaz Modarresi Ghavami	2002	2002	w	Iranian linguist
1966	Kevin McCrudden	2002	2002		American Professor of Religious Studies
1966	Maja Djuric Đurić	2003	2017	w	Montenegrin Associate professor in History of photography
1966	Chika Okeke-Agulu	2004	2004		Igbo-Nigerian artist, poet, art historian, art curator, and blogger (African and African Diaspora art history)
1966	Maryam Iraj	2004	2007	w	Iranian Associated Professor in Linguistics Department
1966	Adisa Imamović	2004		w	Bosnian Professor of English Linguistics
1966	Ugwuona Crescentia	2007	2013	w	Nigerian lecturer of Department of Linguistics, Igbo and other
1966	OLALEYE Samuel Kayode	2010	2012	w	Nigerian Lecturer in African Traditional Religion & Alternative Medicine
1966	Haitham Sukkarieh	2011	2011		Jordanian composer, Professor of Arts
1966	Davor Brđanović	2012			Croatian researcher in Music of Faculty of Philosophy and Religious Studies
1966	Wiwien Widyawati Rahayu	2014	No	w	Indonesian Lecturer of Javanese Literature
1967	Eleanor Dickey	1991	1994	w	American linguist
1967	David Adger	1991	1994		British linguist
1967	Željko Uvanović	1991	2001		Croatian Full Professor of Theory and History of Literature, German
1967	Xavier Soler Àvila	1991	1998		Spanish Independent art historian, documentalist and editor
1967	Bertrand Taithe	1991			British Professor of Cultural History and founding Director of the Humanitarian and Conflict Response Institute
1967	Bruno G. Bosteels	1992	1995		Belgian linguist (Latin American and Iberian Cultures and Institute for Comparative Literature and Society)
1967	Ad Putter	1992			British Medieval English literature and philology
1967	Andreas Roepstorff	1992	1996		Danish Professor, Cognition, Communication and Culture
1967	Marc van Oostendorp	1992	1995		Dutch linguist and Esperantist

1967 Erwan Dianteill	1992	1997		French sociologist and anthropologist
1967 Helen Geake	1992	1995	w	British archaeologist and small finds specialist
1967 Svein Harald Gullbekk	1992	2002		Norwegian numismatist and professor at the archaeological section, Museum of Cultural History
1967 Antonio Cortijo Ocaña	1993	1997		American Professor of Medieval and Renaissance Literature and Culture
1967 Winfried Lechner	1993	1999		Austrian linguist (German linguistics and theoretical linguistics)
1967 Liesbeth Degand	1993	1997	w	Belguian linguist
1967 Matthew Gibson	1993	1993		British Associate Professor of English Literature
1967 Daniuska González González	1993	2008	w	Cuban-Venezuelan professor, researcher, poet, essayist, literary critic and journalist
1967 Bela Tsipuria	1993	1993		Georgian Professor of Comparative Literature (Comparative Literature, Georgian Literature, Modernism, Postmodernism, Postcolonialism), former Deputy Ministry of Education
1967 Elena Anagnostopoulou	1993	1994	w	Greek theoretical linguist and syntactician
1967 Lorenzo Canova	1993	2001		Italian art historian, curator and art critic
1967 Alessandra Petrina	1993	1995	w	Italian Associate Professor of English Literature
1967 Eugenio M. Olivares Merino	1993	1994		Spanish Associate Professor of English Literature
1967 Gregory Anderson	1993	2000		American linguist (Munda languages and auxiliary verbs)
1967 Stolz, Jörg	1993	1994		Swiss Professor of Sociology of Religion
1967 Dr. Nagy Rashwan	1994	2002		British-Egyptian Associate Professor, Department of English, Faculty of Arts
1967 Stefan Weinzierl	1994	1999		German acoustician and musicologist
1967 Detmar Meurers	1994	2000		German Computational linguist
1967 Mehrdad Naghzguy-Kohan	1994	2013		Iranian Associate Professor of Linguistics
1967 Marija Leontik	1994	2009	w	North Macedonian philologist (philology, languages and linguistics and Turkish)
1967 Shannon Lee Dawdy	1994	2003	w	American anthropologist, historian, and archaeologist

1967	Sven Haakanson	1994	2000		American Native American anthropologist who specializes in documenting and preserving the language and culture of the Alutiiq
1967	Paul L Swanson	1994	1994		British the Frances Hill Fox Professor of Religious Studies
1967	Mark Goodacre	1994	2005		British the Frances Hill Fox Professor of Religious Studies
1967	Kristin B. Aavitsland	1994	1994	w	Norwegian art historian
1967	Bahaa-eddin M. Mazid	1995	1999		Egyptian Professor of Linguistics and Translation
1967	Reili Argus	1995	2008	w	Estonian Professor of Estonian Language and the Head of the Estonian Language and Culture Study Area
1967	Gerhard Jäger	1995	1995		German linguist
1967	Taiye Shola ADEOLA	1995	2016		Nigerian lecturer Performing Arts Department
1967	Oktay Ahmed	1995	2005		North Macedonian linguist
1967	Jelena Porsanger	1995	2006	w	Russian-Norwegian (Sami) ethnographer (Sami culture and history)
1967	Antonio Luciano Tosta	1996	2006		Brazilian Associate Professor of Brazilian Literature and Culture
1967	Lutz Marten	1996	1999		British Lecturer in Southern African Languages
1967	Stefan Weber	1996	2001		German Orientalist and director of the Museum of Islamic Art
1967	Thomas W. Murphy	1996	2003		American anthropologist and writer
1967	Mary E. Hess	1996		w	American Professor of Religious Education
1967	Maria Sgouridou	1997	2017		Greek Professor of Italian Literature
1967	Karl Magnus Petersson	1997	2005		Swedish Psycholinguist (Cognitive Neuroscience)
1967	Yasushi Watanabe	1997	1997		Japanese full Professor of Social Anthropology
1967	Greg A. Hill	1998	No		Canadian Audain Chair and Senior Curator, Indigenous Art, National Gallery of Canada
1967	Imre Galambos	1998	2002		Hungarian Sinologist and Tangutologist who specialises in the study of medieval Chinese and Tangut manuscripts from Dunhuang
1967	Amjad Qursha	1998	2003		Jordanian Islamic preacher and a professor (comparative religion and Western Islamic Relations)
1967	Sanjoy Kumar Mallik	1999	2003		Indian Professor of Art History

1967	Magdalena Derwojedowa	1999	1999	w	Polish linguist
1967	Parisa Damandan	1999		w	Iranian photographer and art historian
1967	Aito Ofure	2000	2010	w	Nigerian Senior Lecturer of Literature
1967	Nassar Mansour	2000	2007		Jordanish artist, calligrapher, academic and designer (Islamic Arts, Islamic Calligraphy)
1967	Victor S. Dugga	2000	2001		Nigerian Professor of Theatre and Social Change
1967	Mandana Seyfeddinipur	2001	2006	w	German linguist
1967	Monique Scheer	2002	2006	w	American-German historical and cultural anthropologist
1967	Елена Викторовна Шедова	2002	2002	w	Belarusian art historian
1967	John Timberlake	2005	2012		British painter and Senior Lecturer in Fine Art
1967	Stephen C. Finley	2006	2009		American Associate Professor of Religious Studies and African American Studies
1967	Oqab M Jabali	2009	2012		Palestinean Director of Language Center
1967	Žana Knežević	2011	2017	w	Montenegrin linguist
1967	Obiegbu Ifeyinwa Rita	2014	2014	w	Nigerian senior lecturer in English Language at the department of English and Literary Studies
1968	Johan Bos	1985	2001		Dutch Professor of Computational Semantics
1968	Anupam Ratan Shanker Nagar	1988	1993		Indian Principal of the Gurukul Mahila Arts & Commerce College
1968	Bruce D Willis	1990	1996		American Professor of Spanish and Comparative Literature
1968	Carson T. Schütze	1990	1997		German linguist
1968	Lisa Matthewson	1990	1996	w	Swedish Professor of Linguistics (pragmatics and semantics)
1968	Pradosh Kumar Mishra	1990	2009		Indian Professor of Art History
1968	Mizuko Ito	1990	1998	w	Japanese cultural anthropologist, Professor in Residence at the Humanities
1968	Pavel Janáček	1991	1997		Czech literary historian and critic
1968	Lawrence La Fountain-Stokes	1991	1999		Puerto Rican author, scholar, and performer, gay

1968	Hamid Hassani	1991		Iranian scholar and researcher, concentrated on Persian lexicography, dictionary-making, and Persian corpus linguistics, also an expert on Persian, Standard Arabic, and Kurdish prosody (metrics/ versification)	
1968	Bert Vaux	1992	1994	American Reader in Phonology & Morphology	
1968	Pericles Lewis	1992	1997	Canadian the Douglas Tracy Smith Professor of comparative literature	
1968	Ranko Matasovic	1992	1995	Croatian linguist	
1968	Sadurní Martí	1992	1999	Spanish Associated Professor of Medieval Catalan Literature	
1968	Мальцева Алла Александровна	1992	1994	w	Russian philologist
1968	Dmitri Bondarenko	1992	1993		Russian anthropologist, historian, and africanist
1968	Eduardo Kohn	1992	2002		Canadian Associate Professor of Anthropology
1968	Scott Schwenter	1993	1998		American variationist sociolinguist and pragmaticist
1968	Stefan Müller	1993	1997		German linguist
1968	Ana María Fernández Planas	1993	2001	w	Spanish doctor of linguistics
1968	Gonca Gökalp Alpaslan	1993	1999	w	Turkish reseracher of Department of Turkish language and literature
1968	Carrol Clarkson	1994	1994	w	Dutch researcher (aesthetics, legal theory, and South African literature and art)
1968	Raine Koskimaa	1994	2000		Finnish professor of digital culture
1968	Tobias Scheer	1994	1996		French linguist
1968	Sarah Prescott	1994	1997	w	Irish Professor of English Literature
1968	Jennifer Hay	1994	2015	w	New Zealand linguist
1968	Adam Przepiórkowski	1994	1999		Polish linguist
1968	João Veloso	1994	2004	w	Portugueze linguist
1968	James Loxley	1994	1994		British (Scottish) teacher, researcher and writer (enaissance and early modern poetry and drama)
1968	Louis de Saussure	1994	2000		Swiss linguist
1968	David Brauner	1995	1995		British Professor of Contemporary Literature
1968	Øyvind Ihlen	1995	2004		Norwegian professor and music journalist
1968	Polona Gantar	1995		w	Slovenian linguist

1968-2018

1968	Varmo Vene	1995	2000		Estonian Professor of Semantics of Programming Languages
1968	Matthias M. Tischler	1995	1998		German palaeographer, philologist and historian (multinational and -confessional family with Austrian, Bohemian, French and Hungarian origins)
1968	Reviel Netz	1995	1995		Israeli scholar (Philologist, historian, philosopher)
1968	Alfons Puigarnau	1995	1999		Spanish Associate Professor of Aesthetics, History and Philosophy of Culture
1968	Karma Phuntsho	1995	2003		Bhutanese scholar who specialises in Buddhism, Tibetan & Himalayan Studies and Bhutan
1968	Markus Schlicht	1996	No		French Art history researcher
1968	Josep Lluís Mateo Dieste	1996	2002		Spanish cultural antropologist
1968	Jovan Ajduković	1996	1996		Serbian linguist (Slavic languages, sociolinguistics, contact linguistics, Russian language, Serbian language)
1968	Laura Jiga Iliescu	1996	2003	w	Romanian senior researcher (folkloristic, religious studies, orality and literacy, charms)
1968	Afroditi Athanasopoulou	1996	1999	w	Cypriot Assistant Professor of Modern Greek Literature
1968	Bjørn Thomassen	1996	2001		Danish anthropologist and social scientist
1968	AnneMarie Luijendijk	1996	2005	w	American Professor of Religion
1968	Helena Sablić Tomić	1997	2001	w	Croatian literary theorist and literary critic
1968	Mahmoud Reza Gashmardi	1997	1997		Iranian Professor of french language
1968	Ingūna Daukste Silasproģe	1997	1997	w	Latvian Senior researcher; Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art
1968	Felix Stalder	1997	2001		Swiss lecturer in the theory of the media society
1968	Ulugbek Hamdam	1997	1997		Uzbek writer and translator
1968	Zhao Jin	1997		w	Chinese professor of German linguistics and a scholar in cultural-analytical linguistics
1968	Sherylyn Briller	1997	2000	w	American cultural anthropologist, who specializes in medical anthropology and applied anthropology
1968	Heather Paxson	1997	1997	w	American cultural anthropologist and science and technology studies scholar
1968	Stephen Shoemaker	1997	1997		American Professor of Religious Studies

1968 Farah Mendlesohn	1997	1997	w	British academic historian and writer on science fiction and fantasy literature, and an active science fiction fan
1968 Lizanne Henderson	1997	2003	w	British Senior Lecturer in history
1968 Fernando Zúñiga	1998	2002		Chilean-Swiss linguist
1968 Jean-Noël Lafargue	1998	No		French researcher and blogger in new media art
1968 Ahad Mehrvand	1998	2007		Iranian Associate Professor of English Literature
1968 Le Huy Bac	1998	1998		Vietnamese Professor of Literature
1968 Genevieve Bell	1998	1998	w	Australian anthropologist best known for her work at the intersection of cultural practice and technological development
1968 Dag Øistein Endsjø	1998			Norwegian professor in religious studies
1968 Mirian Tavares	1999	1999	w	Spanish Professor of Visual Arts and Cinema
1968 Joseph Henrich	1999	1999		Canadian anthropologist
1968 Bob Batchelor	2000	2009		American cultural historian and biographer
1968 Deborah Hutton	2000	2000	w	American Professor of Art History
1968 Gunnþórunn Guðmundsdóttir	2000	2000		Icelandish Professor of Comparative Literature
1968 Hürriyet Gökdayı	2000	2000		Turkish Professor of Turkish Language and Literature
1968 Jorge Eduardo Cañas López	2000	2005		Mexican professor og social and culture anthropology
1968 Nataša Tučev	2000	2016	w	Serbian assistant in the English department
1968 Shane McCausland	2000	2000		British the Percival David Professor of the History of Art
1968 Vyvyan Evans	2000	2000		British linguist (cognitive linguistics, digital communication, and emoji)
1968 Aaron W. Hughes	2000	2000		Canadian religious studies scholar
1968 Vesela Chergova	2001	2007	w	Bulgarian Associate Professor of Portuguese Linguistics
1968 Đuro Blažeka	2001	2004		Croatian linguist, lexicographer and expert of the Kajkavian dialect
1968 Mine Bellikli	2001		w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1968 Sem Vermeersch	2001	2001		Belgian Associate Professor, Religious Studies Department
1968 Norma Alzayed	2009	2009	w	Jordanian Professor of English Language and literature

1968 Kelemen Gabriel	2009	2010		Romanian artist and researcher, head of the Art History and Theory department
1968 Safura Borumand	2009	No	w	Iranian Assistant Professor of Iran History
1968 Venera Lljunji	2012	2016	w	Kosovo Professor of the English Language and Literature (Linguistics, Literature, Culture, History, Politics)
1968 Arunkumar	2013	No		Indian Assistant Professor in Costume Design and Fashion (textile painter)
1969 Rachel Nordlinger	1990	1997	w	Australian linguist (Australian indigenous languages)
1969 Joachim Burger	1990	2000		German anthropologist and population geneticist
1969 Jonathan Bobaljik	1991	1995		American Professor of Linguistics
1969 Livio Gaeta	1991	1992		Italian linguist
1969 Eleanor Robson	1991	1995	w	British Professor of Ancient Middle Eastern History
1969 Svetlana Burlak	1992	1994	w	Russian linguist, an Indo-European languages scholar
1969 Álvaro Arias	1992			Spanish Linguist and Hispanist specialist in the fields of Phonology, Morphology and Dialectology
1969 Kaat Wils	1992		w	Belgian researcher of the history of humanities and biomedical sciences in the nineteenth and twentieth century, history of gender, sexuality and the body
1969 Tara Brabazon	1992	1995	w	Australian Dean of Graduate Research and the Professor of Cultural Studies
1969 Jason Baird Jackson	1993	1998		American Director of the Mathers Museum of World Cultures and Professor of Folklore and Anthropology
1969 Giuseppe Solaro	1993	1995		Italian Full professor of classical philology, writer
1969 Rebecca Zorach	1993	1993	w	American art historian and the Mary Jane Crowe Professor in Art and Art History
1969 Andrea Frohne	1994	2002	w	American Associate Professor of African art history
1969 Camille Langston	1994	2002	w	American Associate Professor of English and Communication Arts (rhetorics)
1969 Heidi Harley	1994	1995		American linguist
1969 Uli Sauerland	1994	1998		German linguist
1969 Artemis Alexiadou	1994	1994	w	Greek linguist
1969 Martin Reisigl	1994	2004		Italian Professor of Applied Linguistics
1969 Andrew Carnie	1994	1995		Canadian linguist

1969	Елена Ягунова	1994	1994	w	Russian linguist, Chief of Laboratory of Experimental and Computational Linguistics
1969	Anton Treuer	1994	1996		American native linguist (Ojibwe language and American Indian studies)
1969	Zeresenay Alemseged	1994	1994		Ethiopian paleoanthropologist
1969	Tamara L. Siuda	1994	2008	w	American Egyptologist and author
1969	Berge Traboulsi	1994	No		Lebanese Associate Professor of History, Religion and Intercultural Studies
1969	Anders Klostergaard Petersen	1994			Danish Professor of the Study of Religion
1969	Hilde Van Gelder	1995	2000	w	Belgian director of the Lieven Gevaert Research Centre for Photography, Art and Visual Culture
1969	Catherine E. Léglu	1995	1995	w	British Professor of Medieval French and Occitan Literature
1969	Garbi Schmidt	1995	1998	w	Danish professor in culture and language meeting studies
1969	Art Leete	1995	2000		Estonian Professor of Ethnology (History of Ethnology, History of Ideas, and Anthropology of Religion)
1969	Victor Cojocaru	1995	2001		Romanian reseracher in Black Sea Studies; Classical Archaeology; Ancient History; Classical Philology; Acculturation; Cultural Heritage
1969	Wendy Fonarow	1995	1999	w	American anthropologist, writer, music industry professional and Professor of Anthropology
1969	Tom Beaudoin	1995	2001		American Professor of Religion
1969	Neil McCaw	1996	1996		British Professor in Victorian Literature & Culture
1969	Evelina Mineva	1996	2004	w	Bulgarian Lecturer of Byzantine and Medieval Southslavic Literature
1969	Martin Woesler	1996	1998		German sinologist, cultural scientist and translator of Chinese literature
1969	Unoma Azuah	1996	No	w	Nigerian writer, author, and activist (research on LGBT writing in Nigerian literature)
1969	Mustafa Altun	1996	2003		Turkish associate professor in the field of Philology-Turkish Language
1969	Sophie Marnette	1996	1996	w	Belgian Professor of Medieval French Studies

1969	Kristin Joachimsen	1996	2007	w	Norwegian Professor of the Old Testament/Hebrew Bible
1969	Mirjam Ernestus	1997	1999	w	Dutch Psycholinguistics
1969	Ólafur Rastrick	1997	2012		Icelandic Senior lecturer of Department of folklore/ethnology and museum studies
1969	Labinot Berisha	1997	2011		Albanian assistant of professor of Literature and Language
1969	Fuambai Sia Ahmadu	1997	2005	w	Sierra Leonean-American anthropologist
1969	Jana Riess	1997		w	American author and editor on Religion News Service
1969	Stef Aupers	1998	2004		Belgian cultural sociologist
1969	Eric Fuß	1998	2009		German linguist
1969	Giuliana Pieri	1998	1998	w	Italian Professor of Italian and the Visual Arts
1969	Замалетдинов Радиф Рифкатович	1998	1998		Russian linguist (linguistics, cultural linguistics) фтв увгсфещк
1969	Anne Curzan	1998	2003	w	American linguist (history of English, language and gender, corpus linguistics, historical sociolinguistics, pedagogy, and lexicography)
1969	Cindy Cruz	1998	2006	w	American urban ethnographer and educational researcher
1969	Leslie Van Gelder	1998	1998	w	American archaeologist, writer, and educator
1969	Somfai Kara David	1998	2007		Hungarian academic of Linguistics and Ethnography
1969	Ippei Shimamura	1998	2004		Japanese anthropologist who is best known for his ethnographic work on shamanism and ethnic identity among Mongol Buryats
1969	Derek Kompare	1999	1999		American Associate Professor and Chair of Film and Media Arts in the Meadows School of the Arts
1969	Aline Haas	1999	1999	w	Brazilian Physical Educator, Specialist in Sports Science
1969	Sanja Žaja Vrbica	1999	2011	w	Croatian assistant professor of Art history and Museum studies
1969	Katrin Kivimaa	1999	2004	w	Estonian art historian, cultural critic and translator
1969	Norichika Horie	1999			Japanese Associate Professor of Religious Studies
1969	Mohamed Abdulmajid Akidah	2000	2012		Kenyan Lecturer Linguistics
1969	Andreas Dufter	2000	2002		German Professor Romance Philology (Linguistics)

1969	Shqipe Husaj	2000	2017	w	Kosovo assistant of Professor in linguistics
1969	Pedram Khosronejad	2000	2007		Iranian socio-cultural and visual anthropologist of contemporary Iran
1969	Matthew Wilhelm Kapell	2000	2012		American historian and anthropologist
1969	Jennifer Roberts	2000	2000	w	American the Elizabeth Cary Agassiz Professor of the Humanities at Harvard University
1969	Jeffery D. Long	2000	2000		American Professor of Religion and Asian Studies
1969	James S. Damico	2001	2003		American Professor of Literacy, Culture, and Language Education
1969	Meliha Hrustić	2001	2005	w	Bosnian Professor of German Language
1969	David Salo	2001	2003		American linguist (constructed languages, Tocharian languages, Elvish languages)
1969	Jason Cleverly	2002	2017		British Course leader, 3D Design Camberwell College of Arts
1969	Newsha Ahmadi	2002	2008	w	Iranian Assistant professor of Faculty of Foreign Languages
1969	Anita Hayrapetian	2002	2013	w	Armenian Head of General English Department (Literature, Mythology, Music)
1969	Tamasin Ramsay	2002	2009	w	Australian anthropologist (with a background as an actress), having studied medical anthropology
1969	Mohammad Reza Azadehfar	2004	2004		Iranian Professor in ethnomusicology and santūr performer
1969	George Khut	2005	2007		Australian artist and interaction-designer working across the fields of electronic art, design and health
1969	Karen Wohlwend	2005	2007	w	American assistant professor in the Literacy, Culture, and Language Education
1969	Hana Khalief Ghani	2005	2005	w	Iraqi Associate Professor at the department of translation
1969	Erica Lehrer	2005	2005	w	American anthropologist, curator, and academic specializing in post-Holocaust Jewish culture, museum studies, ethnography, and public scholarship
1969	Andryanto Rikrik Kusmara	2007	2011		Indonesian Associate Professor Dept. of Art Faculty of Art and Design ITB

1969 Yukiko Koga	2008	2008	w	American anthropologist (legal anthropology, urban space, post-colonial & post-imperial relations, history & memory, and transnational East Asia (China and Japan))
1969 Nahidh Falih Sulaiman	2012	2013		Iraqi Head of Department of English (English and American Literature, American theatre)
1969 Theophile Mugisho	2014	No		DR Congolese PhD Student in Gender Studies